

Rice varieties and resistance genes tested for brown planthopper response in China.

Variety	Gene
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>
IR26	<i>Bph 1</i>
IR42	<i>bph 2</i>
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>
H105	<i>bph 2</i>
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>
PTB 21	2 unidentified
PTB 33	2 unidentified
Sinna Sivappu	2 unidentified
Sudu Hondarawala	2 unidentified
TN1	none

10 provinces — Kwangtung, Kwansi, Fukien, Chekiang, Hupeh, Hunan, Kweichow, Szechuan, Anhwei, and Kiangsi (see figure). They infested TN1 seriously but were light on Mudgo, IR26, ASD7, Rathu Heenati, Babawee, PTB 21, PTB 33, Sudu Hondarawala, and Sinna Sivappu.

Survival of BPH nymphs on TN1 was significantly greater than on varieties with resistance genes. TN1 supported a larger population and allowed greater development of BPH.

The area of honeydew stained by ninhydrin on TN1 was greater than the area

Distribution of brown planthopper biotypes in China.

on resistant varieties. The heaviest honeydew was excreted by BPH fed on TN1. ■

The results indicate that BPH collected from the different regions of China are biotype 1. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Inheritance of tolerance for aluminum toxicity in Brazilian rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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Four Brazilian upland rice cultivars — Pratão, IAC 25, Perola, and Bico Ganga — and their F₁ and F₂ progenies from a diallel cross were evaluated for response to 0, 30, and 60 ppm Al in nutrient solutions. The characters studied were plant height, root length, and shoot and root dry weight of 25-day-old seedlings after 21 days of growth in the solutions.

Pratão and IAC 25 were more tolerant of aluminum toxicity than Pérola

and Bico Ganga. At 0 ppm Al, Pratão had shorter stems (2%), shorter roots (10%), and less dry weight (49%) than Pérola, but at 60 ppm Al had longer stems (23%), longer roots (15%), and greater dry weight (195%).

Tolerance for aluminum toxicity was controlled by more than one pair of genes, with transgressive segregation and quantitative inheritance observed. Specific combining ability was more important than general combining ability, indicating a greater nonadditive genetic factor. Specific combining ability for all the characters studied at different aluminum concentrations was least in the Pérola-IAC combination. Genotypic correlations were greater than phenotypic correlations, indicating that genetic components had greater contribution than environmental components. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Sensitivity of some modern rice varieties to high temperature at anthesis in the western districts of Orissa, India

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Anthesis or blooming is the only growth stage at which rice plants are sensitive to high temperatures. Spikelet sterility is mainly attributed to pollen desiccation. Jennings and others found some varieties, such as Hoveyze from south Iran, fertile at temperatures higher than 45° C when others are sterile.

Preliminary observations on the effect of maximum day temperature during

Effect of different maximum day temperatures at blooming on spikelet sterility of different varieties Orissa, India.

Variety	Date of 50% flowering	Max temp (°C)	Sterility (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Subhadra	10 Mar 1980	32.5	11.0	2.3
Bala	16 Mar 1980	39.0	39.4	2.1
Parijata	20 Mar 1980	39.5	9.4	3.8
Rajeswari	30 Mar 1980	33.5	19.9	4.1
Suphala	1 Apr 1980	38.0	28.5	3.6
Kumar	5 Apr 1980	37.5	62.4	2.9
Ratna	-do-	-do-	49.4	3.2
IR36	-do-	-do-	25.8	3.1
IR32	-do-	-do-	26.6	3.4
Annapurna	-do-	-do-	18.1	3.8
Rasi	-do-	-do-	37.3	3.2
Pusa 2-21	-do-	-do-	34.0	3.3
Jatjati	-do-	-do-	34.4	4.6
Jaya	25 Apr 1980	44.5	17.3	4.9
Hema	-do-	-do-	23.7	4.7

anthesis on spikelet sterility of 15 high yielding modern rice varieties at the RRS, Chiplima showed a wide spectrum of resistance to high temperatures at blooming (see table). Kumar suffered the most with a temperature of 37.4° C at anthesis; its sterility percentage was

62.4. Parijata suffered the least with a higher temperature of 39.5° C at anthesis; its sterility was only 9.4%. With a still higher temperature of 44.5° C — often the maximum temperature for this tract — the sterility percentage was only 17.3 in Jaya and 23.7 in Hema. ■

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Pest management and control DISEASES

Host range of *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Thanatephorus cucumeris* in the Vietnamese Mekong Delta

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After a 3-year survey of rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 9 hosts of *Pyricularia oryzae* and 27 hosts of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* were collected. These hosts were determined according to Koch's postulate.

Hosts of *P. oryzae* (a causal agent of rice blast disease) were *Brachiaria mutica*, *Digitaria* sp., *Echinochloa colonum*, *Echinochloa* sp., *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *Polytrias amaura*, and *Sacciolepis* sp.

Hosts of *T. cucumeris* (causal agent of sheath blight of rice) were *Glycine max*, *Zea mays*, *Sorghum vulgare*, *Saccharum officinarum*, *Alternanthera repens*, *Brachiaria mutica*, *Brachiaria distachya*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Cyperus pilosus*,

Cyperus haspan, *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Echinochloa colonum*, *E. crus-gulli*, *E. cruspavonis*, *Eleusine indica*, *Fugraea colhinchinensis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Heydystis bryonii*, *Leptochloa chinensis*,

Leersia hexandra, *Lindernia pedunculata*, *Monochoria hastata*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *Sacciolepis interrupta*, *Scirpus grossus*, *Scirpus articulatus*, and *Neyraudia reynaudiana*. ■

Correct schedule of cypermethrin spray for RTV control

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Trials at PES have shown that rice tungro virus (RTV) can be controlled by

foliar spray with cypermethrin. It was also observed that spraying after the 15th DT (day after transplanting) alone was not as effective as spraying on the 15th DT. To determine the correct crop stage to spray and optimum number of cypermethrin spray for effective RTV control, a detailed study was conducted

Data on rice tungro virus incidence and grain yield. Tamil Nadu, India, 1980-81 thaladi. ^a

Treatment ^b	Rice tungro (%)		Stunted unproductive population (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	AV	TV	AV	TV	
Control	76.9	61.3	46.8	43.2	2.8
One spray: 7th DT	34.6	36.1	16.9	24.3	4.3
Two sprays: 7th and 14th DT	18.5	25.5	0.5	4.1	5.4
Three sprays: 7th, 14th, and 21st DT	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1	5.9
Four sprays: 7th, 14th, 21st, and 28th DT	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1	6.0
C.D. (P = 0.05%)		8.4		6.2	0.369

^aAV = actual percentage of RTV, assessed with disease counts taken from the field. TV = transformed value for the actual percentage of RTV incidence. ^bDT = day after transplanting.